

TABLE I— γ_2 AND γ_3 TRANSITIONS IN HALOCOBLTATES(II)

$$B=(nC_4H_9)_4N^+; E=(C_2H_5)_4N^+; M=(CH_3)_4N^+$$

Compound	$\gamma_2(\text{cm}^{-1})$ (Aceto- nitrile)	$\gamma_3(\text{cm}^{-1})$ (Aceto- nitrile)	$\gamma_3(\text{cm}^{-1})$ Reflec- tance	$\gamma_3(\text{cm}^{-1})$ (OH_2NO_2)
$M_2(CoCl_4)$	15385	5236	15150	15267
$E_2(CoCl_4)$	15314	5263	—	15150
$E_2(CoCl_2Br_2)$	15198	5348	14749 ¹	15106
$E_2(CoCl_2I_2)$	14970	5464	14388 ¹	14925
$E_2(CoBr_2I_2)$	14535	5495	13889	15106
$M_2(CoBr_4)$	14815	5291	14493	14815
$M_2(CoCl_6)$	15270	5291	15267	15267
$E_2(CoCl_4)$	15150	5208	15198	15106
$E_2(CoCl_4Br)$	15340	5291	14925	—
$E_2(CoCl_2Br_2)$	15270	5291	14815	15198
$M_2(CoCl_2Br_2)$	15150	5376	14993	15106
$E_2(CoCl_2Br_2)$	15040	5348	14641	15038
$M_2(CoCl_2Br_3)$	15340	5361	14641	15038
$E_2(CoCl_2Br_4)$	15200	5348	14706	15150
$M_2(CoBr_2)$	14815	5291	14600	14706
$B_2(CoCl_2I_2)^*$	15200	—	14430	15198
$E_2(CoBr_2I_2)^*$	14600	—	13986	14600
Equimolecular Mixture of $E_2(CoCl_4) + ECl$	15150	5208	—	15106

* γ_2 bands were not observed fully.

expected order, that is, $Cl^- > Br^- > I^-$, γ_2 values are reverse of the expected order (Table I); this may be attributed to high absorption by the solvent in the near i. r. region or possibly the solvent interacts with the complex ion in some other way than simple coordination.

Mixed Pentahalocobaltates(II): We have concluded from the electronic spectral (nujol mull) and far i. r. studies³ that the mixed pentahalocobaltates(II), in fact, are double salts containing tetrahedral cobalt e. g., $(CoCl_4Br)^{3-}$ is $(CoCl_3Br)^{2-}Cl^-$. The solution is similar to that in Cs_3CoCl_5 which has been shown to be $Cs_2CoCl_4.CsCl$ by crystallography⁸. The γ_3 values for the mixed pentahalocobaltates(II) are nearly the same as for the corresponding mixed tetrahalocobaltates(II) and they also show a similar trend (Table I). This supports the assumption that similar ions are present in the solution of both the halocobaltates(II).

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Preparation and Characterisation of μ -Dihydroxotetrakis(Salicylato)-Diaquodichromium(III)

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GILLARD¹ and coworkers have studied oxidative degradation mechanism of coordinated salicylic acid in form of *bis*(ethylenediamine)salicylato-cobalt(III) and have reported that the reactivity of salicylate is markedly modified by coordination. Complexes of cobalt(III) containing the bidentate salicylate ion undergoes reaction in which the organic moiety is modified while remaining bound to the metal ion. While trying to extend the study to other salicylate complexes, it was found that the salicylate complexes of many metals including those of transition metals have been reported by a number of workers²⁻⁵ but most of these studies have been carried out in solution. In this paper we report the preparation and characterisation of μ -dihydroxotetrakis(salicylato)diaquodichromium(III) by analysis, derivatographic study, i.r. spectra, magnetic susceptibility measurements, U.V. and visible reflectance spectra. Lastly the oxidation of the complex was carried out in 12 N sulphuric acid medium.

The instruments used and method of preparation of the complex have been described earlier^{6,7}. The percentages of chromium were determined volumetrically⁸. C and H were estimated by element estimation technique. Complete analysis gives (Found Cr = 14.2%, C = 45.9%, H = 3.9%, calculated for $[Cr_2(OH)_2(OHC_6H_4COO)_4(H_2O)_2]$ Cr = 14.4%, C = 46.45% and H = 3.7%). The stages of oxidation were followed potentiometrically⁹ using bright platinum electrode on a Chrompton potentiometer. The concentrations were so chosen that 10 ml of M/1120 μ -dihydroxotetrakis(salicylato)diaquodichromium(III) requires 10 ml of M/60 $K_2Cr_2O_7$ for complete oxidation to CO_2 stage.

Derivatographic Study:

The combined D.T.G., D.T.A. and T.G.A. curve of a sample of 500 mg of the complex μ -dihydroxotetrakis(salicylato)diaquodichromium(III) was carried out with heating rate of 8°/min. The temperature was fixed between 30° to 800°. The summary of the results is tabulated in Table.

The first three products were confirmed by i.r. spectra, chemical tests and element estimation technique. The metal carbonate was confirmed by chemical tests and quantitative liberation of CO_2 . The final product was confirmed by powder X-ray analysis.

TABLE

D.T.G. curve reading (in °C)	The compound formed and the loss in weight in T.G.A. curve	Nature inflexion point of the peak in D.T.A. curve in °C
60-140	$[\text{Cr}_2(\text{OH})_2(\text{OHC}_6\text{H}_4\text{COO})_4]$ 24mg	Endo at 130
150-240	$[\text{O}\{\{\text{Cr}_2(\text{OHC}_6\text{H}_4\text{COO})_4\}\}]$ 37mg	Endo at 240
240-310	$[\text{O}\{\{\text{Cr}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{COO})_2\}\}]$ 237mg	Endo at 270
310-470	$[\text{Cr}_2\text{O}(\text{CO}_3)_2]$ 331mg	Exo at 360 Endo at 460
470-600	Cr_2O_3 391mg	Exo at 550 Endo at 600

Endo=Endothermal peak, Exo=Exothermal peak.

I. R. Spectra, Magnetic, U. V. and Visible Reflectance Spectra :

The i.r. spectra of the complex was carried out in nujol mull, magnetic and reflectance spectra were taken in solid phase at room temperature. The i.r. spectrum of the complex $[\text{Cr}_2(\text{OH})_2(\text{OHC}_6\text{H}_4\text{COO})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ exhibits a strong and broad band at 3450 cm^{-1} and a sharp band at 960 cm^{-1} attributed to bridged hydroxyl group in the complex¹⁰. The broadening of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ vibration at 1595 cm^{-1} and splitting of $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ vibrations into two bands 1370 cm^{-1} and 1308 cm^{-1} indicates that some of the salicylic acid molecules are coordinated to Cr(III) atoms through both the carboxylic and phenolic oxygen while the rest are monocoordinated. The medium bands at 1620 cm^{-1} and 808 cm^{-1} are attributed to coordinated water molecules.

The magnetic moment value of the complex was found to be 3.45 B.M. The electronic reflectance spectra exhibit two bands at 16390 cm^{-1} and 23810 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g(\text{F})}$ and ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g(\text{F})}$ transitions respectively in octahedral ligand field. The lower magnetic value¹¹ and 10 Dq value^{12,13} in the present case might be due to bridged nature of weak ligand field energy of salicylate group.

Oxidation :

The very sharp inflexion obtained at 3.8 ml after 3 hrs storage at room temperature corresponding to 10 electron abstraction stage per molecule of salicylic acid and the i.r. spectra indicate the destruction of aromatic ring. The intermediate stage could not be identified. At 12 hrs storage at room temperature a very sharp inflexion point was obtained at 5.0 ml i.e., 14 electron abstraction per salicylic acid molecule. The products obtained at this stage were characterised as *bis*(maleato)diaquochromium(III) and *bis*(oxalato)diaquochromium(III) complex as intermediate products spectrophotometrically and by paper chromatography. On prolonged storage at room temperature (240 hrs) inflexion point was obtained at 7.8 ml corresponding to 22 electron abstraction. The oxidation product of coordinated salicylate was identified to be predominantly *cis-bis*(oxalate)

diaquochromium(III). The complete oxidation of coordinated salicylate to carbon dioxide and water takes place only after heating at 90° for 18 hrs.

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Synthesis of 5-Hydroxy-3', 4', 5', 7-Tetramethoxy-8-Prenylflavanone

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5-HYDROXY-3', 4', 5', 7-tetramethoxy-8-prenylflavanone has been synthesised by a new route, involving lesser number of steps and in better yield, starting from 4-*o*-methylphloroacetophenone¹ which on prenylation gave two compounds, identified as 4-*o*-methyl-3-prenylphloroacetophenone(I) and gem-di-C-prenyl-4-*o*-methylphloroacetophenone(II) on the basis of spectral data. Ketone (I) on condensation with 3, 4, 5-trimethoxybenzaldehyde² under alkaline conditions gave the title compound (III) which agreed in its characteristics with the sample prepared earlier³ by a different route. Methylation of III yielded IV which was also made from the corresponding chalcone⁴(V).

Experimental

Prenylation of 4-*o*-methylphloroacetophenone :

To an ice cold solution of 4-*o*-methylphloroacetophenone (5 g) in alcoholic KOH (3g in 50 ml)